

Agro2Circular

D7.2 – Public Engagement Strategy & summary of Activities and Results

September 2023

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Technical References

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
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Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D7.2
Dissemination Level*	PU
Work Package	WP7 – A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability
Task	T7.2 – Public Engagement Strategy & summary of Activities and Results
Lead Beneficiary	KVELOCE
Contributing Beneficiary/ies	UVEG, ICONS, CARM, INFO, EURA, CJM, AGRO, PRIMA, PROEX,CETEC
Due Date	30 September 2023
Actual Submission Date	30 September 2023

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document History

V	Date	Comments
0.1	30/08/2023	First draft of document
0.2	25/09/2023	Revised version
1.0	29/09/2023	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
1.1		First draft based upon first final version
2.0		Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	30/08/2022	UVEG, ICONS, CARM, INFO, EURA, CJM, AGRO, PRIMA, PROEX, CETEC
v.0.2	25/09/2022	CETEC and ICONS for peer review
V1.0	29/09/2023	Coordinator for submission

Verification and Approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Aran Blanco	29/09/2023
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó	29/09/2023

Disclaimer and Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838

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2 List of Abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
AoM	Agenda of Meeting
AGROFOOD	Agrofood cluster of the Region of Murcia
D	
CARM	Autonomous Community of Region of Murcia
CDS	Communication and Dissemination Strategy
CETEC	Technological Centre for Plastic and Footwear of the Region of Murcia
CETENMA	Technological Centre for Energy and Environment of the Region of Murcia
CEBM	Circular Economy Business Models
CJM	CAJAMAR Foundation
CIFEA	Integrated Centre for Training and Agricultural Experiences
CTNC	National Technological Centre for Canning Industry
DoA	Description of the Action
Dn.n	Deliverable (number)
DIS	Data Integration System
ExC	Exploitation Committee
F2F	Face to face
GA	General Assembly
IAP2	International Association of Public Participation
INFO	Development Institute of the Region of Murcia
KPIs	Key performance indicators
MCT	MOCITOS
M	Month
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PRIMA	Primafrío Foundation
PROEX	PROEXPORT
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SP	Stakeholder Panel
Tn.n	Task (number)
UPCT	Polytechnical University of Cartagena
UVEG	University of Valencia
WPn	Work Package (number)

3 Glossary

Co-creation: Process for collaborative knowledge generation by academics working alongside other stakeholders, promoting meaningful interactions and better utilisation of products and resources.

Description of the Action: In an H2020 project, the DoA is a document that captures the essence of the envisaged solution in the form of high-level needs and features that gives the reader an overview of the final project deliverable(s). It includes the project work plan and information regarding the project scope, cost, time and risks, as well as information such as milestones, deliverables, and project organisation and approach. The DoA contains the project charter and the project work plan of a PM² project.

Face-to-face infrastructure: In the context of public participation processes, face-to-face participation structures include those in which people can physically see one another, in person (meetings in the same room) or virtually through teleconferences to enable citizen engagement at all levels.

Public engagement: It is understood as the myriad of ways in which the activity and benefits of higher education and research can be shared with the public. Engagement is a two-way process involving interaction and listening and to generate mutual benefit. The concept is considered a synonym for public participation and/or citizen engagement and both terms will be used throughout the document.

Virtual infrastructures: In the context of public participation processes, virtual infrastructures comprise of online platforms, application software and collaborative channels that assist purposeful citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower) within a given territory (municipality, region, country, EU).

4 Executive Summary

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.2 *Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results* and is a summary of activities and results of the Agro2Circular project undertaken within task 7.1.1 *Public engagement strategy*, updating D7.1 *Public Engagement Strategy* launched in M12 (September 2022) with the activities implemented and the lessons learnt during the first and second years of the project, to be applied at the European level in the D7.16 *Report on potential for adoption and scale-up potential* of the A2C project and other EU regions, namely Lombardy (D7.17) and Lithuania (D7.18).

The objective of the public engagement strategy in A2C is to contribute to the co-design and acceptance of the A2C multidimensional model and to demonstrate the adoption in the Murcia A2C cluster and its replication & scale-up potential. The public engagement strategy has a regional scope (the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community), while a community-based innovation scheme is based at the local level in one of the municipalities (within T7.1.2).

D7.1 aimed at designing the conceptual framework and the strategy for the Public Engagement (Section 5), based on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders for the public participation at the region and local level (Section 6) and the selection of suitable resources, key actors and the A2C infrastructure for the citizen engagement (Section 7). Those chapters are summarized in this report and new paragraphs were marked and highlighted as [updated / new] for the convenience of the reader.

The aim of D7.2 is to report the main outputs of the Public Engagement strategy put in place during M12-M24, including the activities performed until M24 of the project such as the set-up of participatory bodies providing recommendations and selecting the most suitable resources to be used during the last year of the project (M24-M34) in the A2C citizen engagement. Furthermore, the action plan (section 8) is briefly updated with priorities and activities to be deployed in the following period. The main results will be further developed in the final version of this deliverable.

Finally, the dissemination and communication measures are defined in Section 9, refining the guidelines provided in D7.1. The conclusions and lessons learnt will be further explained in D7.3 (M34, July 2024) and, for the specific case of the activities performed by PRIMAFRIO in Task 7.1.2 (*Community-based innovation schemes*) in D7.4 (M35, August 2024).

5 Agro2Circular Engagement Process

A2C public engagement strategy was designed following a four-steps process including ecosystem analysis, diagnosis, action plan and communication. The strategy is based, in fact, on the analysis of the existing infrastructure, processes and relevant stakeholders relying on the **Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders** model (Figure 1) for the public participation at the regional (Region of Murcia Autonomous Community) and local level (for the community based innovation scheme in Alhama de Murcia). The selection of suitable resources and key actors from civil society, business and industry, research and education allows to benefit from synergies and to avoid an overlapping of measures or citizens overburden.

Figure 1 Quadruple Helix of Stakeholders

The diagnosis of the participation level entailed the analysis of the Project actions, framed in the 5 level of participation defined by IAP2 Core Values for Public Participation¹ (Figure 2), the needs and priorities of the region to deploy a circular economy, and the setup of the engagement infrastructure. The action plan then builds on the existing resources and relevant actors and concretises the participatory activities according to the level of participation entailed by the A2C interventions at the regional and local level, aligned with the goals of the specific action, its complexity and sensitivity. The A2C communication measures to ensure the public engagement were also defined to ensure a meaningful adoption, replication & scalability of the A2C systemic solution model.

¹ <https://www.iap2.org/general/custom.asp?page=corevalues>

Figure 2 Spectrum of Public Participation. Source: Vancouver Mayor’s Engaged City Task Force. Final Report. (2014) based on IAP2 Spectrum of Public Participation

For further understanding of this document, other deliverables related to the public engagement strategy should be considered:

- The A2C project DoA, which is Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement number 101036838 and contains the details of how the action (project) will be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- The A2C Public Engagement strategy (D7.1; M12) that defines the Public Engagement approach followed in the project.
- A pilot community-based innovation action (T7.1.2) aiming at public engagement will be implemented, promoting circular social practices among citizens and raising awareness will be arranged within WP7. The lessons learnt and the impacts will be reported at M35 (D7.4).
- The evaluation framework and methodology (D7.5; M9) drafted in T7.2, provides guidelines for monitoring and assessment of the public engagement strategy and the transition towards circularity.
- The socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (D7.8; M18) provides a first approximation to assess the socioeconomic feasibility of the A2C project and an initial estimation of the potential impact of the A2C solution considering dimensions at territorial/community level representing a "social thermometer" to the action in the organisations representing the different value chains in the Region of Murcia; therefore, it provides an evidence-based ground for future experiences and the updates of the public participation strategy. The final results of socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis will be included in D7.9 (M36).
- The Dissemination and Communication strategy (D8.1, M4), drafted under T8.1, aims at supporting the public engagement, spreading awareness and general knowledge and public awareness about food and plastic waste and the circular economy concept. It also includes guidelines for the communication focused on local and

regional level, to be carried out in T8.3 (Communication and engagement at local and regional level) led by PRIMA.

- The Toolkit of Guidelines and Training Materials (D8.6; M18), will include lessons learnt to be shared with other initiatives working on community-based research, participatory methods and education for environmental issues or local climate change mitigation as well as those targeting cluster and industry about circular business models, financing and regulatory issues. This deliverable will be updated through D8.7 (M36) including the final version of the toolkit.

The A2C public engagement strategy was deployed in D7.1 following a **four-step process**, detailed in sections 6, 7, 8 and 9.

1. **Ecosystem analysis** (Section 6): This section gathers information on existing resources for public participation in the region of Murcia (cluster level) and the municipality of Alhama de Murcia (local level), both in terms of relevant infrastructure and stakeholders. The ecosystem analysis was performed in D7.1 and will be summarised in this report.
2. **Diagnosis** (section 7): In which the virtual and F2F infrastructures detected in the ecosystem analysis and suitable for the A2C project are selected, drafting recommendations and analyzing the level of participation required in the action plan, to determine the infrastructures that must be designed.
3. **Action Plan** (section 8): Based on the ecosystem analysis and the diagnosis, this section is an action-oriented timeline in which key resources and responsibilities are defined together with concrete activities. The action plan is dynamic, and therefore developed in a collaborative way, revised and adjusted along the project lifecycle. In this deliverable, the actions carried out until M24 will be analyzed and new activities to be performed during the last year of the project will be planned.
4. **Dissemination and Communication** (section 9): Complementary to the full dissemination and communication strategy described in D8.1, describes further the communication plan and features of the local outreach desk.

6 Ecosystem Analysis

This section aims to analyze the existing citizen engagement infrastructures and processes, to ensure the efficiency and effectiveness of the A2C citizen engagement strategies in the region of Murcia. The use of these infrastructures in the A2C project will be further explained in the section diagnosis, and action plan.

The region of Murcia is located in southeast Spain, limited to Alicante (Valencian Community) in the northeast, Almeria (Andalusia) in the southwest, Granada and Jaen (Andalusia) in the west, and Albacete (Castilla- La Mancha) on the north. It is confirmed by 45 municipalities. Specifically, pilot activities for citizen engagement will be carried out in the Municipality of Alhama de Murcia, in the centre of the region (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Region of Murcia and the municipality of Alhama de Murcia. Source: IDERM

Therefore, the ecosystem analysis will cover these two levels (regional and local). This engagement strategy is complemented at the EU level by the activity 8.5 led by EURADA and detailed in the related deliverables, from which further lessons will be extracted that can be applied at the local and regional level, and vice versa.

The activities developed under the engagement strategy and their results will be studied in terms of replicability and transferability to other regions and countries at the EU level, to be included in the D7.16 *Report on potential for adoption and scale-up potential* of the A2C project.

6.1 Analysis of the Citizen Engagement Infrastructure [updated]

6.1.1 Regional Level

6.1.1.1 Virtual

Virtual infrastructures comprise online platforms, application software, and collaborative channels having as a purpose citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower), in the region and its municipalities.

6.1.1.1.1 Region of Murcia Participation Platform

The Region of Murcia participation platform (<https://participa.carm.es/>, Figure 4) responds to the regulation document (Law 12/2014 of the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community) that recognises the rights of citizens to participate in public affairs and requests the implementation of measures and tools to articulate this participation, applied within the scope of public administration of the Region of Murcia Autonomous Community and entities

conforming the public sector. It is aimed at the Region's citizens as well as citizen organisations having the region as their main area of activity.

participación ciudadana
REGIÓN DE MURCIA

UNIÓN EUROPEA

Participación ¿En qué participo? Ámbitos Fomento Subvenciones

Consultas Públicas

Qué son y cómo se realizan las Consultas Públicas

Las consultas públicas son un procedimiento estructurado de la Administración Regional para recabar opiniones, propuestas y sugerencias de la ciudadanía.

Los órganos administrativos o entidades competentes que consideren oportuno abrir un proceso de participación ciudadana que contemple estas consultas publicarán en esta plataforma la versión inicial del proyecto de norma, plan, procedimiento o instrumento administrativo, junto con la documentación complementaria necesaria para su comprensión y evaluación.

A continuación se describe en una infografía el proceso y se listan todas las consultas publicadas, indicándose el estado y la tipología:

Participación

La ciudadanía expresa su opinión y realiza sugerencias y propuestas a la iniciativa del Gobierno, a través de un cuestionario accesible normalmente por Internet.

Resultado

Una vez cerrado el cuestionario en línea, se elabora y difunde un *Informe de Aportaciones Ciudadanas*, que recoge las opiniones y propuestas de las personas y entidades que han participado en la consulta.

Decisión

Las aportaciones ciudadanas son valoradas y se someten a decisión del órgano directivo responsable, que indicará las propuestas estimadas o no estimadas, en su caso, en un *Informe Razonado de Decisión* que se publica en esta Plataforma.

CONSULTAS PÚBLICAS ACTIVAS

Figure 4 Citizen participatory platform (Region of Murcia)

This technological platform is managed by the CARM and specifically, by the Office for Transparency and Citizen Participation (OTPC). It allows the diffusion, and the management of the citizen participation tools, promoting channels to interact with regional administrations in designing and evaluating public policies. The website also includes links to different territorial scopes of participation, such as the municipalities, communities of citizens from Murcia in other Spanish regions and abroad, participation at the national and the EU level, as well as resources and information for associations. Other contents provide information on activities to promote citizen participation, such as workshops or funding.

Currently, the platform foresees 5 types of participative processes: citizen contributions, public consultations, participative deliberation processes, citizen participation forums and citizen initiatives: Currently, there are no open participatory processes.

The platform also communicates through Twitter using the account [@RMTransparencia](https://twitter.com/RMTransparencia)

6.1.1.1.2 Open Data Region of Murcia

The URL of the portal is <https://datosabiertos.regiondemurcia.es/>.

This website responds to the commitment of the Region of Murcia administration to join the Open Data Initiative. The website works at the Inform level, providing data on a wide range of indicators (environmental, social, economic). Data can be used to generate applications and services. Currently, two applications are already launched: AGROCLIMA (integrated management of meteorological data with open access for agricultural planning, developed by the Institute in Murcia for Agricultural Innovation and Research – IMIDA) and Agenda Regional – Region de Murcia Digital (for mobile devices, providing information on next events extracted from the Region of Murcia digital portal, developed by an SME). Although there are no applications on the topics related to the circular economy, the platform includes a section where citizens can suggest the development of other services. Thus, this space could also host the data integration system, in the form of a link, generated in the A2C project.

6.1.1.1.3 Open Knowledge Site of the Region of Murcia

URL: <https://conocimientoabierto.carm.es/>

It is an open access repository where documents are stored and disseminated using normalised protocols to ensure the visibility of the documents and their authors, in such a way they are findable by specialised and generalist search engines.

The repository was initiated as a training modality by the public administration school in 2011 and became a project for knowledge management in 2014 collecting digital contents from research, technical reports and other publications from the Region of Murcia. The website is currently coordinated by the transparency office of the Region of Murcia, while the document upload is overseen by designated persons in charge of each collection depending on the topics covered (Agriculture, Livestock and Fishing, Social Policies, European Union).

6.1.1.1.4 Transparency Site of the Region of Murcia

This website can be found at URL <https://transparencia.carm.es/>.

It responds to the obligation of the autonomous community to provide active advertising that is regularly updated and published without an explicit requirement by the citizenship, thus ensuring the transparency that constitutes the first level of public participation (Inform) regarding institutional and organisational information, relationships with society, regulations, contracts and agreements, grants and subsidies, as well as information on budgets, properties, assets, land planning and environment. The information provided refers to the public administrations, autonomous bodies, public entities, foundations, and consortiums.

The website includes information on corporate and civic participation bodies, the regulatory frameworks governing them, their sessions and the agreements achieved. The bodies that may be related to A2C will be further explained in section 6.1.1.2 of this deliverable.

The transparency platform also includes links to the open data website and the participation website.

Other communication channels are:

- Twitter <https://twitter.com/RMTransparencia>
- YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnaWZAz4krBWI3GVcJw6wvA>

6.1.1.1.5 SITMURCIA: Geoportail of the Region of Murcia Spatial Data Infrastructure [updated]

This service can be accessed at <https://sitmurcia.carm.es/>.

Integrated into the Spanish Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDEE), the Region of Murcia Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDERM) provides georeferenced data on different thematic areas, that can be visualised (thus relevant for transparency and information) using a GIS visor (hosted) or WMS/WMTS services (Figure 5).

Figure 5 SIT MURCIA (Geoportal) homepage

Particularly, the thematic area infrastructures and equipment are included, through the Local Infrastructures and Equipment Survey (EIEL), a qualitative and quantitative analysis tool of the services under the competencies of municipalities, allowing the distribution of resources and the planning of public investments. The survey for the Region of Murcia (EIEL-CARM) can be accessed through the IMIDA: https://geoportal.imida.es/eiel_carm/

Among the infrastructures and services included, it provides information on the location of different bins (paper/board, plastic, organic, batteries) as shown in Figure 6 for Alhama de Murcia.

Figure 7 Screenshot of Plataforma Tierra

This infrastructure was initially considered of interest for the engagement of local actors for the community-based scheme: for instance, to host the information on bins installed to collect food waste. Nevertheless, it was later discarded, due to the punctual allocation of the bins during the days when Task 7.1.2. was carried out.

6.1.1.1.6 Plataforma Tierra [updated]

The Plataforma Tierra (Tierra Platform, URL: <https://www.plataformatierra.es/>) is owned by the CAJAMAR non-profit foundation partner of the A2C Project, created by the Cajamar credit cooperative bank private funding entity. It is available in English.

The platform allows to register as a user through a form, the compulsory fields being personal data (name, surname), the field of activity (Agriculture/Livestock, Industry and services, Knowledge, Public Bodies and Associations, Financing, Consumers, others) and fields of interest (including different types of crops and livestock species).

After registering, the platform offers a summary of upcoming events and meteorological predictions (Figure 7) as well as information on key agricultural indicators (market prices), links to videos and news.

In the top bar, the main menu is included with the following sections: **Markets**, **Innovation**, **Tools**, and **Training**.

Figure 8 Training section of Plataforma Tierra

The section Tools is being considered for including a link to the A2C Data Integration System (DIS) in development under WP1 (Task 1.5). The section Training is currently being considered to offer courses under T8.6, aimed at different professionals and including technical and financial aspects of circular economy.

6.1.1.2 Face-to-Face

Face-to-face participation structures include those in which people can physically see one another, in person (meetings in the same room) or virtually through teleconferences.

6.1.1.2.1 Sectoral Councils

Different types of collegiate bodies operate in the Region of Murcia, among which those related to the topics of A2C will be described. These bodies meet the requirement of the government (President, Vice-president, or Regional Councillors):

- **Regional Agricultural Advisory Council:**
- **Regional Advisory Council of Agriculture Professional Organisations.**
- **Regional Environmental Advisory Council:**
- **Regional Advisory Council of Social Economy:**

In addition, the following bodies are technical and consultative boards that provide qualified advice on the issues considered by the President or Vice-President:

- **Regional Consumption Advisory Council:**
- **Regional Advisory Council on Citizen Participation.**

6.1.2 Local Level

The City Council published the Regulation on Citizen Engagement in 2012 (BORM 20/02/2012²) which details the processes and bodies involved. In the regulation, different levels of public participation are covered. In this way, the regulation sets the means and the channels for the Inform level, as well as the Consult level, through public surveys and questionnaires. In addition, it regulates the right to participation, through propositions, and the arrangement of public consultations and referendums. The regulation also foresees the foundation of associations and entities for public participation at the local level, the potential funding through subsidies, their inclusion in the local register of these associations, and their participation in local decision-making bodies.

In addition, the City Hall implemented the Strategy for Sustainable and Integrated Urban Development (EDUSI) 2017-2023, which includes a **specific plan for citizen engagement** collecting contributions from different social and economic agents, experts, technical and political staff and citizens, which included a process for citizen engagement through meetings, forums and local assemblies, on specific topics and also transversal issues.

6.1.2.1.1 Virtual

The website of the Councillorship of Public Participation³ offers different opportunities for public participation.

- Participative budgets (last process in 2021).
- Agenda Urbana 2030: the agenda is currently being developed to deploy the SDGs at the local level. A virtual survey was open until June 2022 to collect feedback from

² <http://transparencia.alhamademurcia.es/transparencia-municipal/reglamento-de-participacion-ciudadana/>

³ <https://ayuntamiento.alhamademurcia.es/areas/area.asp?id=29>

citizens on different topics, including environmental awareness, mobility, and waste recycling. As a result of the consultation, an initial diagnosis document was published in February 2023⁴.

Moreover, there is a website called Alhama Suma (<http://www.alhamasuma.es/>), directly related to the EDUSI, in which citizens can give their opinions on the strengths and weaknesses of the city in different areas: Environment and Climatic Change, Infrastructure and Services, Natural and Cultural Heritage, Society and Demography, Economy and Employment, and an additional space where citizens can provide suggestions.

6.1.2.1.2 . Face-to-Face

The city of Alhama has two stable bodies for public face-to-face participation:

- The Local Council of Economy and Employment (since 1998) comprises 19 economic and labour organisations.
- The Local Assembly of Citizen Engagement (since 2012) comprises 26 neighbourhood associations and social organisations.

6.2 Stakeholders and Services

The stakeholders and services related to the engagement strategy in the Region of Murcia and the municipality of Alhama, which are relevant for A2C topics, will be mapped in this section.

Several sources of information were taken into account for the purpose all along the project lifecycle:

- Regional register of associations (especially those on agriculture, environment protection and consumers).
- Sociograms and lists of key actors are to be developed within the participatory processes realised in the region and the municipality.
- Consultations with key stakeholders and experts in the region.

Key actors are identified within the following profiles according to the Quadruple Helix of Open Innovation: Public Administration/Public Services; Private Sector (Industry); Citizens and Civil Organisations; and Research and Education.

The key actors and services are listed in D7.1 and in this deliverable are included as Annex.

6.2.1 Public Administration/Public Services

Stakeholders in the public sector were gathered from institutional websites, at the regional and local levels. The selection criteria to be included as relevant were their relationship and competencies in the fields of environment, economy, regional development and research and education.

6.2.2 Private Sector (Industry)

Stakeholders in the private sector were gathered using search engines (Google). In the case of the agri-food sector, the websites of partners AGROFOOD and PROEX and previous meetings held with these partners provided information on existing actors, since these

⁴ <https://datos.alhamademurcia.es/descargas/918s-agenda-urbana-alhama-prediagnosticofeb22.pdf>

partners are themselves associations of businesses. The actors selected can be considered examples, since only those devoted to the production and exportation of the crops studied in the project are detailed, avoiding an excessive extent of this document. In the case of plastics, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals, the businesses in these subsectors were selected from the website of the Association of Chemical Industries in the Region of Murcia (AMIQ). Likewise, commercial centres and supermarkets delivering food (fruits and vegetables) that may be involved in the circular economy model proposed by A2C and can be found through the register of the Commerce Chamber of Murcia⁵ were considered to be of interest due to the retail delivery of food and the use of fruits and vegetables generating waste at greater scale than citizens (and sometimes packed in plastics). The inclusion of tourism and hospitality services is based on their identification as an area of consumption where food loss and waste are significant issues [2], with these two sectors taking a high weight in the Region of Murcia. Finally, regarding the financial sector, the entities with the most presence in the agricultural sector have been selected.

6.2.3 Citizens and Civil Society Associations

The associations included at the regional level rise as the result of searching within the Regional Register of Associations of the Region of Murcia⁶. In the association type field, “Amas de Casa/Consumidores/Usuarios” (Housewives/Consumers/Users), “AMPAS” (Associations of Parents of Schoolchildren), “Ecologistas” (Environmentalists), “Educativas” (Educational), “Federación” (Federation), “Profesionales” (Professionals) and “Vecinos” (Neighbours) are included.

For the case of the local level, an additional filter (Municipality) was included in the search in the mentioned register to include only those located in Alhama de Murcia.

6.2.4 Research and Education

At the regional level, the sector of research and education comprises the three universities: UM and UPCT are public, and together comprise the Campus Mare Nostrum, while UCAM is a private university. All of them have university chairs (Cátedras Universitarias) related to the topics of A2C.

Education at the local level comprises primary and secondary schools. The centres included have been searched through the Regional Ministry of Education in the Region of Murcia (EDUCARM⁷). We have focused on Alhama de Murcia, where the Community based engagement models will be tested during T7.1.2 but other centres may be added at the regional level. Special attention was paid to those that have already implemented zero waste activities⁸, an initiative promoted by the collective “Teachers for future Spain” (<https://teachersforfuturespain.org/>), which brings together teachers of the whole country who implement actions to move towards sustainable management of Spanish schools and the development of environmental education.

⁵ <https://www.camaramurcia.es/censo-de-empresas/>

⁶ Link to [Search form at the Register](#)

⁷ <https://mapaescolar.murciaeduca.es/mapaescolar>

⁸ [Map of schools with Zero waste initiatives](#)

7 Diagnosis

The Diagnosis phase defines the contextual basis for the action plan to be specified in the following section.

Based on the previous analysis of the existing infrastructures, the bodies and spaces of participation that are existing and relevant for A2C co-creation processes are selected in this section. They are both institutional and private, as well as those resulting from previous participatory processes. The infrastructures identified will be involved in the A2C citizen engagement.

The knowledge acquired in the previous ecosystem analysis has also allowed the detection of potential strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (barriers) for the implementation of participative processes foreseen in the A2C project that is organised in the form of a SWOT matrix.

Subsequently, the levels of participation required by co-creation and citizen empowerment processes are analysed to determine the actions that are more appropriate for the action plan (section 8).

Finally, the virtual and face-to-face infrastructure that must be created in order to implement the engagement strategy (together with the existing ones) is proposed.

7.1 Selection of Existing Infrastructure [updated]

The analysis of the existing virtual and face-to-face infrastructures for participation at the regional and local levels resulted in the selection of those that could be used within A2C (Table 8), due to their relevance to the project topics (Circular Economy, Environmental Management, Social Economy, Public Engagement) and the scope of the project. For example, the provision of information, spaces for collecting feedback from civil society and fostering participation and collective decision.

After one year of the project, some of the infrastructures (Table 1) have been marked in grey, due to inactivity (no updated information in the respective portals)

Table 1 Virtual and face-to-face infrastructures for participation at regional and local level

Type	Regional Level	Local Level
Virtual	Region of Murcia participation platform SIT Murcia (geoportal) Open data platform Transparency site Plataforma Tierra	Councillorship of Commerce and local development [updated] Alhama Suma
Face-to-face	Regional Agricultural Assessment Council Regional Assessment Council of Agriculture Professional Organisations. Regional Environmental Assessment Council	Local Council of Economy and Employment Local Assembly of Citizen Engagement

Regional Consumption
 Assessment Council
 Regional Assessment Council
 of Social Economy
 Regional Assessment Council
 on Citizen Participation

Further key alliances will be identified based on the analysis of the key stakeholders, getting at relevant actors missed in previous projects. Collaborative workshops with stakeholders (section 8.1) are used as a tool to identify their key alliances, action sets and feasibility. Questionnaires are being performed along the project implementation aimed at the different stakeholders to visualize the degree of affinity with the project objectives and their capacity to influence in this context.

Moreover, once the agents are mapped, the results of the indicated tools (questionnaires, workshops) are analyzed to establish action sets that will gather agents with common positions as well as possible conflicts existing in the territory; likewise, feasible alliances will be identified, both for strengthening the connection between stakeholders and for managing conflicts.

7.2 Preliminary Review [updated]

During the A2C kick-off meeting, the presentation of the WP7 included three preliminary questions for the partners involved with their existing networks and channels that could be useful for the project. The answers obtained were used as a first step for the ecosystem analysis. As a result of this analysis, a preliminary SWOT matrix was elaborated (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Preliminary SWOT matrix: engagement processes for the implantation of the circular economy

At the end of June (M9) under WP7 activities (T7.1) a workshop was organized in Alhama de Murcia (where the coordinators and other partners are based) aiming at analyzing the existing spaces for collaboration in the project. The activity is fully described in section 8.

7.3 Levels of Participation in A2C Activities [updated]

A2C foresees the citizens’ engagement process in the Region of Murcia entailing different levels of participation, based on the *Spectrum of Public Participation* developed by the International Association of Public Participation (IAP2), as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Levels of public participation.

Source: <http://tompkinscountyny.gov/tccp/publicparticipation>

The spectrum ranges from low participation, where people are simply informed about the relevant problems and alternative solutions (on websites for example) to high participation, where they are empowered to take the final decision on the issue at hand (i.e., through deliberative forums or referendums) [1].

The spectrum levels within the A2C project will be applied as follows:

Citizen engagement goal: To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed.

Information only involves a one-way flow of information from the project to citizens, although it is an important foundation for community engagement since it builds knowledge and allows citizens to understand the public decision-making process and take informed decisions. The Inform level of public participation gives citizens what they need to fully understand the project’s actions so that they can reach their own conclusions. Some authors ([2], [3]) consider that the Inform level should be placed across the spectrum, since effective engagement requires effective information. This way, although informing does not involve

community participation per se [4], it increases the understanding of the issues, the ability of the stakeholders and communities to address them, and the compliance with regulations [5].

The Inform level is appropriate in situations where there is no opportunity for the public to influence decision-making. Simply informing them is the appropriate activity. Indeed, all the relevant stakeholders (administration, business, academia, and civic society) will be targeted at the Inform level on all the activities and results of the A2C project through the project website (<https://agro2circular.eu/>), social media (@Agro2Circular), scientific dissemination, press releases, flyers and brochures specially designed for the local level. In addition, a local website will be developed by the WP8 leader (ICONS) including specific information in the global contexts, and spaces for participation (questionnaires, surveys, events) to be managed by the Local Outreach Desk (PRIMA, KVC) and WP7 partners will use their websites (i.e. CARM: [section of Regional Ministry of Agriculture](#)) as an information platform on the news and events carried out in the project. Moreover, lectures, workshops, open visits and seminars on site are planned by the partners (AGRO, PRIMA, PROEX). These activities overlap and are to be coordinated with those in WP8. Specifically, the following actions will be taken:

- (i) Meetings with stakeholders (i.e., the association of food industries AGRUPAL) that will be potential future users of the process, model and valorisation technologies.
- (ii) PROEX as producers and exporters will also inform their associated partners in internal assemblies and using their internal channels.
- (iii) Third parties' events such as the Science Week Fair organised by Fundación Seneca, held every year at the end of October/beginning of November at the Malecon Park (Murcia) where technological parks (CETEC; CTNC) have a dedicated stand, will constitute an opportunity to engage users through posters and small experiments or merchandise related to the project to general society (families, schools), policy-makers and industry. AGROFOOD also collaborates in this event.
- (iv) Awareness raising talks will happen in primary/secondary schools, VET centres, universities and companies. In this regard, PRIMAFRIO organised these talks, that were also conducted by KVC, and CETEC. AGROFOOD has already taken part in regional events disseminating the A2C projects to the wide public (as part of WP8, T8.3) establishing a basis for further contacts with potential attendants in future activities.
- (v) Training activities (included in T8.6) aim to train professionals (active and potential), unemployed people as lifelong training, universities (through related chairs, some of them already backing the project through letters of support) and cover not only technical and technological aspects, but also the financial and perspectives (especially for companies).
- (vi) A stand at the local weekly market in Alhama de Murcia (held every Tuesday, 9:00-14:00) will be managed by PRIMAFRIO, to provide information to visitors and vendors about the project and to distribute materials (brochures, flyers). KVC, CNTC and AGROFOOD provide support to this activity, collaborating in the stall; a shift planning will be established among these entities to optimise

the efforts and offer different types of specific information to the stakeholders interested.

- (vii) Scientific and professional dissemination: as stated in the A2C outreach strategy (D8.1): scientific dissemination of the project results is planned along the project implementation, in the form of papers in peer review journals and contributions to congresses and conferences. Publication of papers in professional journals will also contribute to the engagement of the industry in the adoption of the A2C model. In this regard, AGROFOOD is invited by the editorial board of the CTNC biannual magazine (**CTC Alimentación**⁹), published in printed form for the agri-food sector in the region but also available online. This professional magazine has already published information on the project.
- (viii) Industry fairs and events: It is also planned to participate in events such as fairs, symposiums and brokerage events in different sectors. For instance, CTNC and AGROFOOD are involved in the organisation of the International Symposium on Food Technologies, a meeting point for companies in the sector that takes place coinciding with the [Murcia Food Brokerage Event](#) organised by INFO (held in May 2023). Likewise, CETEC took part in the AGRICULTURAL FILM Conference (March 2023).

Citizen engagement goal: To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.

Promise to the public: We will keep you informed and will acknowledge concerns and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

The Consult level of public participation focuses on feedback and is the basic minimum opportunity for the public to input on analysis, alternatives or decisions. The responsibility for the decisions remains with the government or the organisations doing the consulting (i.e., the project manager).

The Consult level is appropriate when specific input is sought from citizens for the decision-making, but early engagement is not possible throughout the process. There is a wide range of ways to perform consultations, some of which include processes that require little or no dialogue (surveys in a newsletter or digital platform) or involve a debate (public meetings, focus groups).

Several activities in the Region of Murcia and their community-based schemes require the willingness of stakeholders (among them citizens) to provide information.

- (i) Surveys about awareness of citizens and companies: covering i.e., their consumption and disposal habits of fruits, vegetables and plastic packages, as well as recycling behaviours to improve the effectiveness of the A2C systemic

⁹ <https://ctnc.es/publicaciones/>

- solution model, while reducing the cost of implementation. The surveys would be tailored depending on the sector/group.
- (ii) Surveys aimed at the private sector: input from companies will be required to explore the adoption possibilities and viability analysis (covering economic benefit) of the A2C solution including the data integration system and the business models developed. The viability analysis will also cover the logistic aspects of the circular solution, such as the responsibility of the collection and storage or the benefits foreseen. It gives consideration for the additional costs which stakeholders incur in the adoption of such practices. Feedback on problems of interest in the sector will also be gathered, such as finding biobased products that fulfil their requirements and subsidising options.
 - (iii) Consultations on training needs will be aimed at different publics, including VET and assimilated (vocational training, lifelong learning) on existing gaps in curricula on circular economy so that university (undergraduate, MSc) as well as companies recognise their needs for unmet skills.

These surveys will be hosted on the A2C platform and the website (in a specific section). The partners will contribute to obtaining results with links on their websites (especially institutional partners) on the level of awareness of the circular economy. In addition, the EU Platform EUSurvey (<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/>) will also constitute a useful tool for consultations.

Citizen engagement goal: To work with the public to make sure that concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.

Promise to the public: we will work with you to ensure that your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.

At the Involve level, citizens are invited into the process to a greater extent than at the Consult level. The goal is to work with the public throughout the process and to make use of their knowledge and expertise on a given issue. This implies a two-way exchange of information that encourages discussion while providing an opportunity to influence the outcome. The Involve level not only ensures a common understanding, but also the products or services provided are better tailored to the stakeholders' needs. The regulation, standardisation or behaviour needs are accepted and sustainable and the resources are effectively applied at this level.

At the Involve level, the public is invited into the process, usually from the beginning, and is provided multiple opportunities for input as decision-making progresses. However, while 'Involve' assumes a greater level of participation by stakeholders as they work through issues and alternatives to assist in the decision-making process, the organisation undertaking the engagement generally retains responsibility for the final decision. In A2C,

the Involve level will be mainly implemented in the co-creation of the multidimensional model and in the community-based scheme. Some of the activities at the involvement level are:

- (i) Collection of materials (F&V waste, multilayer plastic) to be incorporated into the circular value chains. Agri-food companies (farmers and the juice industry) are involved in the project collecting multilayer plastics and F&V waste to be processed by the technological partners.
- (ii) Video game contest for students: organised by PRIMAFRIO, the aim of the contest is to engage students to develop video games in specific workshops on circular economy and programming. It has been joined with the eco-school award initiative. The City Halls of Murcia and Alhama also collaborate in this activity, and the contest's first edition (pilot) will be presented in September 2022 and expanded in the next school year (2023-2024). The project will seek support in schools that are already implementing zero waste initiatives.
- (iii) Edition of a documentary: this activity can also be considered as part of the community-based scheme. The documentary will follow the process in the market, the start of the waste collection and the collection itself, and the shipment to the entities that process the wastes (CETEC, CTNC). Some issues to be confirmed in this activity will be the level of involvement of the participants and the scope (local or regional).
- (iv) Involvement in the circular economy using biobased packaging: PROEX as a representative of 56 entities of the agri-food sector (industry) has declared their interest to be users of the biobased packaging developed within the project.
- (v) Involvement in waste collection in markets: led by PRIMAFRIO in the community-based scheme (T7.1.2). Two associations of markets (sellers) have been already contacted to explain the project and request collaboration and transfer to the CTNC. Waste (leftovers) from the vending stalls is collected. The containers are provided by PRIMAFRÍO. This activity raises the need for dissemination of materials in Spanish, mentioned in the Inform level above, which will be addressed in section 9.

Other activities included at this level are, i.e., workshops, focus groups on innovative business schemes and social sustainability indicators accompanied by volunteering days (in clean-ups). These activities will be carried out in collaboration with AGROFOOD, due to their wide experience in dissemination of the circular economy and organisation of workshops.

Citizen engagement goal: To partner with the public in each aspect of the decision-making.

Promise to the public: We will seek direct advice and innovation in formulating solutions from you. Your advice and recommendations will be incorporated into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.

At the Collaborate level, the public is directly engaged in decision-making in an interactive process with an emphasis on two-way processes. The Collaborate level of public engagement includes all the elements of Involve but takes it a step further, including an explicit attempt to find consensus solutions. However, similar to the Involve level of participation, the administration or project management board remains the ultimate decision-maker.

At this level, it is important to create trust and to ensure that there is genuine engagement, and this can be costly and time-consuming. Besides, there can be risks involved in processes at this level. If the promise is seen as being broken (e.g., if members of a community cannot agree on ways forward, or if some sections of the community feel their views were not taken into account), trust can be broken and future relationships with key stakeholders can be significantly damaged. The Collaborate level is particularly useful for controversial issues and complex problems because it entails a high level of participation. In A2C, the Collaborate level is represented by the stakeholder panels, which will be created to bring together partners and representatives of organisations, industrial companies, and associations which are relevant in the A2C's results uptake. The panels will make recommendations on the necessary features of the project's results, as well as on the systemic circular solution. In addition, stakeholders will contribute to building new market routes and implementation vehicles in different industrial sectors. Related to the demonstration activities, online meetings, pop-up activities, and workshops for stakeholders will be organised to gain specific feedback from the A2C targeted sectors. Moreover, the collaboration will be sought with projects funded under the same call and topic: FRONTSHIP (), Circular Foam (<https://circular-foam.eu/>) and EcoeFISHent (), are examples, although this list will be updated along the project in upcoming versions of this document. Moreover, collaboration is also planned with projects in similar calls; for instance, A2C (represented by AGROFOOD and CTNC) has already participated in a workshop organised by PestNu () project. During the project implementation, new stakeholders will be contacted by KVC as systemic approach manager to join the stakeholders' network of A2C, using mailing rounds, through the EU Circularity Platform or participation in related discussions during significant events (i.e.) and they will be invited to join one project meeting per year where possible, in addition to other specific meetings. At this stage of the project, two panels are being created: one of them at the local/regional level, and an international stakeholder panel. The criteria for selection of the stakeholders' panels will be the representativity of each sector in the quadruple helix (Figure 1), the interest of the project reflected through Letters of Support, and the existence of previous contacts among the partners. At the current stage of the project, we have the following members who are: UNC Unione Nazionale Consumatori Umbria and Sammontana.

Citizen engagement goal: To place final decision-making into the hand of the public.

Promise to the public: We will implement what you decide.

At the Empower level, the public has the opportunity to make decisions for themselves, which implies a shared responsibility for making decisions and accountability for the outcomes of these decisions.

Empower represents the most challenging approach in community engagement, since it represents a commitment by the initiators (administration, government, project management board) to participate as a stakeholder and to share power in decision-making for collaborative actions.

The benefits of the empower level are often more innovative results, reduced conflict in controversial issues and greater commitment to ongoing actions. Nevertheless, it does not necessarily require great interaction between citizens and decision-making organisms. Some examples of this level are a referendum, participatory budgets and other ballot measures. Legislative and policy frameworks also give power to communities to make decisions, although this term may be misleading, since it may involve delegating the authority of administrations or policy-makers [3]. It should also be highlighted that the Empower level may incur a high risk of tokenization, and paperwork and bureaucracy often wear down active citizens [6].

Within the A2C project, the Empower level will sit at an operational level, rather than a decision-making level, providing opportunities and resources for communities to directly contribute to the solution, valuing local talents and skills and acknowledging their capacity to be decision-makers in their own lives [2].

7.4 A2C Virtual and Face-to-Face Infrastructure [updated]

7.4.1 A2C Virtual Infrastructure [updated]

In addition to the already existing participation infrastructures mentioned in section 6.1, the following virtual channels and sites will be used for the A2C public engagement:

- **Web platforms**

- A2C website (<https://agro2circular.eu/>) – active, managed by ICONS as WP8 leader. The website homepage (Figure 11) includes information on the project (why, what, how, where, who), resources to download (deliverables, flyer, postcard), and news at EU level. It is linked to the Spanish version through the menu.

Figure 11. A2C website homepage (What? section) in English

A2C local website: in development. It will be managed by PRIMA as partner leading the local outreach desk, and KVelocity responsible for the engagement strategy. It is expected that the local A2C project will reproduce the general project website, but with the addition of detailed information on the pilot demonstrators, the community-based scheme and the A2C systemic model including all the relevant factors (governance, regulation, policy, financing, etc.). It will also include adapted communication materials (brochures, posters, etc.) and news and activities for the implementation of A2C participatory processes: proposals, forums, consultations, calls for meetings, workshops, or ballots. The technical features of the local website are under discussion and development.

Figure 12. Event created for the Hoop Biowaste Club

Current status

On M10 (October 2022), a Spanish section was added to the A2C website to inform stakeholders on the activities developed at the local and regional level; to avoid linguistic barriers, this section is in Spanish language. Two types of publications are used: It is managed by KVC, in collaboration with PRIMA for the generation of contents. Other partners (CETEC, PROEX, AGROFOOD, DOMCA, CTNC) also provide information and news for the local website.

- Events: This category is used to announce future events and activities, in which the public is called to participate. As an example, the Science Week performed

in Murcia in October 2022, or the Biowaste Club in which A2C took part as a network event in April 2023 (Figure 11).

- **News:** News pieces are uploaded once the activities have taken place, summarising the main results and conclusions. News is published on the Spanish section of the website approximately twice a month, to ensure that the public remains engaged. Up to the publication date of this deliverable, 17 news items have been published at the local and regional level.

- **Social networks:** The Twitter channel (@Agro2Circular) and the **official hashtag #agro2circular** have been set, as well as the LinkedIn profile. Other social networks may be used if relevant, under the decision of the local outreach desk and according to the dissemination and communication strategy (D8.1).

Current status

According to D8.1, a Twitter profile (@Agro2Circular) and the official hashtag #agro2circular, as well as the LinkedIn profile were set. Nevertheless, these social media offer information in English language; the labelling of the main profile in the partners' social media profiles allows the publication in Spanish language while ensuring a wider dissemination.

In April 2023, a Youtube Channel was opened, in which short videos were uploaded depicting the multidisciplinary scope of the project and the role of different stakeholders in the circular economy related to the agrifood sector. UP to date, 11 videos have been uploaded. This channel will also host a documentary prepared within a participatory approach (see involve level, section 8).

7.4.2 A2C Face-to-Face Infrastructure [updated]

Different structures and spaces for public participation will be created within the A2C Project. Some of them are proposed at this stage of the participation strategy and their creation and functions (meeting periods, composition, tasks) will be further discussed along the project implementation:

- **A2C Space at the regional level:** This space will be aimed at providing information on the project and the systemic circular solution of A2C. The local outreach desk will deploy a stand at the local market (near the zones dedicated for food stalls, see Figure 13 and Inform paragraph in section 0) on a regular basis, from October 2022 to the end of the project, where information on the project will be provided and the activities will be carried out. A space in Alhama de Murcia will be also requested from the City Council, as a supporting entity where participatory events, seminars, workshops and meetings will be held. It will also be the office of the local outreach desk.

Current status

Up to the date of this deliverable, information regarding the project is available at the Local Development Office of the Alhama City Council, in the form of brochures. This office has also hosted meetings with stakeholders for the preparation of Task 7.1,2. Nevertheless, due to space limitations, the space is not fully dedicated to the project. From November 2023 (M14) to June 2023 (M21), a booth was installed every 2 weeks at the Alhama city market within the activity T7.1.2. The activity has been interrupted during the summer months, due to the high temperatures (weather alerts), but will be restarted in October 2023 until the end of the project. This booth acts as a space fully dedicated to the project. Further information is provided in section 8.

The networking activities carried out by the project have also allowed the availability of spaces for the organization of participatory events, seminars, workshops and meetings, such as the Circular Education Lab in Murcia, aimed at the awareness raising and the widespread of circular practices.

Figure 13 Zones of the Alhama market with food stalls (marked in light green). One of the areas is located around the food market hall (Mercado de Abastos), marked with a shopping cart in the map.

- **Coordination and Management Group:** This group will be composed of the partners responsible for the public participation methodology of the project. They will establish agile and flexible governance systems to ensure the smooth communication and coordination towards all stakeholders (policy makers, industry, research and education, and citizens). The coordination and management group will

coordinate the different bodies created for the engagement process and act as mediator in case any controversy arises.

Current status

The Coordination and Management Group has been set up by KVC and PRIMA. They hold regular meetings (approx. 1 per month) to supervise the performance of the activities being carried out as part of the Public Engagement, and to coordinate the Local and Regional Dissemination and Communication according to the project needs, ensuring the wider outreach. CETEC as project coordinator supports this coordination and management group, providing advice and means to achieve the desired objectives (contacts, requirements to partners, information).

- **Driving Group:** This group will be built in Q3 2022 after the circular economy workshop held in Alhama de Murcia in June 2022. The group will act as a local stakeholder panel, composed of representatives of the key stakeholders from the quadruple helix of social innovation: University of Murcia, Regional Development Agency (INFO), Industry (AGROFOOD, PROEX, CJM), Regional and Local initiatives, CSOs, together with KVelocity (Systemic Approach Manager) and PRIMA (Local Outreach Manager). Their main objectives are to generate synergies with other existing and ongoing projects at the local and regional level, organising activities, seeking mutual support, and detecting solutions for the implantation of the circular systemic solution.

Current status

The Driving Group acts as part of the local stakeholder panel set up for the project. It is composed by the partners based in the region of Murcia: Regional Development Agency (INFO), Industry (AGRO, PROEX, CJM), Research (CETEC, CTNC) and public Administration (CARM), together with KVelocity (Systemic Approach Manager) and PRIMA (Local Outreach Manager). Up to date, three workshops have been held, further detailed in sections 8.1 and 8.2 (Collaboration level).

8 Action Plan

8.1 Regional Workshop on Public Engagement [updated]

Under WP7, a regional workshop on public engagement was planned for June 2022 in Alhama de Murcia at the regional level to establish a participatory approach toward the stakeholders' needs and priorities. Moreover, this workshop served to nurture further public engagement activities. It was organised to identify the interest, opinions, and wishes of the partners involved in WP7 at the regional level and to detect potential infrastructures and analyze synergies and barriers. The workshop represented a key point for organising the community-based scheme.

Current status

The workshop was organized by KVC and attended by CETEC, PRIMAFRIO, AGROFOOD, PROEXPORT, CAJAMAR, and CARM, constituting the first meeting of the Driving group.

During the workshop, participative methodologies were used to explore the opportunities for engagement at the regional and local scales. First, shared in groups their interests and prospects, based on the 5 levels of engagement of the IAP2; thereafter, during a plenary session, the proposed activities were displayed on a panel (Figure 14). Most of the activities were framed in the inform, consult and involve levels. During this session, the infrastructures of public engagement in A2C were also discussed. These results were already reflected in D7.1, as the activities to be carried out at the different levels of IAP2.

Figure 14 Panel of opportunities for public engagement

Subsequently, another plenary session was conducted to explore barriers and framework conditions for the engagement activities (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Plenary session

Among the aspects to be considered, the following are to be highlighted:

- The need of dynamizing the Spanish section of the website, to constitute an effective tool for engagement (to be discussed with WP8 Leader ICONS).
- A framework condition that may difficult the involvement of agrifood companies was the legal definition of waste according to Law 7/2022 for waste and contaminated soil¹⁰, which considers waste as materials that an agent discards or has the intention to discard. This definition leaves agrifood waste as outgrades, that are already used in the canning industry or food for livestock.
- Regarding the multilayer plastics used for mulching, partners called attention to the inconsistencies related to the types that are being recommended and subsidized by regional authorities, although they are not biodegradable.
- The availability of some agrifood waste is limited in time by seasonality. The suggestion of exploring other types of food waste is subject to technical justification.
- The need of communicating financial and economic aspects, beyond technical dimensions, targeting professionals and companies through dedicated training was also underlined.

8.2 Public Engagement Activities [updated]

In the current document, a preliminary list of activities suitable for each level of participation is proposed. Nevertheless, it must be taken into consideration that the action plan is dynamic, and these will be updated in a collaborative manner, with contributions from all partners in subsequent workshops.

¹⁰ <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2022-5809>

8.2.1 Inform [new]

As mentioned, the aim of the inform level of public participation is to provide balanced and objective information promptly to the public. This implies to give citizens what they need to fully understand the action and to reach their own conclusions.

Table 2. A2C Inform activities schedule

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024
Website/ social media		Public launch		Spanish section								
Seminars webinars								SMEs and Sustainability				
Exhibitions/ events					Science Week	FOOD BE		Science Week				Science Week
Demo sites							CETEC GREEN WEEK					

Information on the website and social media: As indicated before (section 7.4.1, a Spanish section of the website was created. Initially, this section included general information on the project, but later a blog structure was included to upload Events (Eventos) and News (Noticias), as seen in Figure 16. 17 News pieces and 3 Events have been published up to date.

Figure 16, News and Events at the Spanish section of the website

Next steps

The activity at the website and social media will be maintained, with the aim at dynamizing the contents.

Some of the planned news that are pending to be published in the next months will be the PROEXPORT Assembly in which the project will be promoted, as well as their participation in FRUIT ATTRACTION fair; the launch of the videodocumentary and a report on the “making-of”, or the continuation of the activity at the Alhama city market.

In the last year of the project, it is expected to include other resources in the website, such as best practices regarding community-based social innovation schemes for circular economy (gathered as a result of T7.1.2) , surveys and questionnaires (under different activities, such as T7.4, T7.5 or T8.6), the video documentary shot to explain the different dimensions of the project deployment (under T8.3), or announcing site visits to the project demonstrators (under WP6). Further information on the website and social media can be found in the Dissemination and Communication report (D8.2; M18).

PRIMA as local outreach manager elaborates a calendar and requires partners for contributions to the website.

. Webinars and seminars. The organization of webinars and seminars has been focused to educational purposes, and carried out by PRIMA, KVC, CETEC and AGROFOOD aimed at the different levels (primary and secondary schools, vocational education and university). Three different topics have been addressed so far: a general seminar on circular economy, and two specific seminars on plastic upcycling and the application of biotechnology to circular economy. The seminars started in February 2023 and were carried out until May 2023; during this period 16 Workshops/seminars were held, in 8 different educational centres, with the attendance of more than 400 students. In addition, CETEC took part as speaker in a webinar organized by the Technological Centre on Environment of the Region of Murcia (CETENMA) and AGROFOOD in a webinar organized by the University of Alcalá - Analytical Chemistry area in the subject "Use of waste from the food industry".

Next steps

For the scholar year 2023/2024, a new series of workshops/lectures are being prepared, together with the corresponding materials such as presentations; to this end, PRIMA has already arranged meetings and procedures with the educational centres and the Regional Ministry of Education. Furthermore, other seminars and webinars are being organized targeting different stakeholders, such as professionals or enterprises, to engage them in the implantation of the circular economy, with the participation of CETEC, KVC and AGROFOOD. More detailed information on the contents can be found in Deliverable Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (Draft; D8.6, M18).

INFO will soon present a mapping and best practices in Circular Economy. Moreover, they are organizing for November 2023 an event “Pymes and sustainability”, a training session focused on social impact, good governance and environment, and will provide the participants with tools to elaborate policies for sustainability, in which the project will be presented due to the close relationship with the topic.

Expositions and attendance to events. All along the project, partners have been participating in expositions and scientific and technical events, raising the awareness of the public from all sectors of the stakeholder helix on the challenges addressed by A2C and the solutions proposed to achieve the circularity of the agrifood sector. Some examples of this activity are the Science Week held in Murcia in October 2022, in which the technological centres CTNC and CETEC were present in a booth together with AGROFOOD (Figure 17); Innovam+22 held in Cartagena attended by AGROFOOD and CTNC in October 2022; attendance and

presentation of results at International congresses in September 2022, April and July 2023; the Murcia FOOD Brokerage Event organized by INFO in collaboration with CTNC in May 2023 (Figure 18); Crecestartup Agrifoodtech held online June 2023 with the participation from AGROFOOD and CTNC, or the FAME- INNOWA fair attended by PROEXPORT in April 2023. Further information on these activities can be found in the Dissemination and Communication report (D8.2; M18).

Figure 17. Exposition on multilayer films at CETEC/CTNC booth. Murcia Science Week 2022

Figure 18 Murcia FOOD Brokerage Event 2023

Next steps

For the next year of the project (2023/2024) it is expected to participate in the new edition of the Science (October-November 2023) and Innovam+. CAJAMAR will also present the project in the Science Week held at University of Almeria, at the end of October 2023. In addition, partners are expected to attend various events related to the theme of A2C that will be announced in the coming months or where we are invited.

Site visits. Up to date, CETEC has already performed site visits coinciding with the Green Week (June 2023, Figure 19).

Figure 19. Students during the site visit to CETEC, Green Week 2023

Next steps

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Several visits will be realized to the 9 demonstrators planned under WP6, allowing citizens to fully understand the actions' features and implications. Besides, the visits will enhance the character of implementation action demonstration objective of the project. The visits will start progressively, according to their progress by the responsible partners, and will target representatives of the quadruple helix of open innovation: public administration and public services; private sector; citizens and civil society organizations; and research organizations and universities. Besides, special attention will be paid to young people and the site visits will be offered to students in the region, paying special attention to primary and secondary schools, vocational training and university degrees with close relationships to the project's topics in the region (CIFEAs, environmental sciences, biotechnology, chemistry, agricultural/industrial/chemical engineering, to mention some).

8.2.2 Consult [new]

The objective of the consult level is *to obtain feedback on analysis, issues, alternatives and decisions.*

Table 3. Consultations timetable

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024
Surveys and questionnaires for soc. Analysis					T7.4			T7.4		T7.4, T7.5	T7.4	
Surveys at community-based scheme							Market prize					
Other Consultations							T7.5	T7.5, T8.6	T8.6			

Socioeconomic Analysis: Under T7.4, the socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis required the participation of the stakeholders participating in two of the value chains addressed in the project (lemon pulp and peel, and disinfection film); the analysis is embedded in the evaluation framework, using the social organisational Lifecycle assessment (SO-LCA) approach. A questionnaire was answered by 115 workers at the regional level. Additional information on the methodology and the results can be found in the Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (D7.8; M18). A parallel consultation was run targeting stakeholders' managers, while VTT collected information for the environmental LCA (T7.3). For the purpose of this deliverable, it is worth highlighting that the questionnaire included different sets of questions, aimed at analysing the awareness and consciousness regarding circular economy, through selected questionnaires, as well as the environmental concern measured using the revised NEP (New Ecological Paradigm) scale [7], [8]. The results obtained can be considered as a screening.

Next steps

Further consultations (Table 3) are expected targeting wider samples in the last year of the project, framed under the socioeconomic/sociocultural analysis (T7.4) with results to be published in the final version of the Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (D7.9; M36); furthermore, these results will be valuable for the validation and clustering of the A2C model at the EU level (T7.7), allowing an evidence base assessment of its potential for adoption and scale up reflected in the corresponding report (D7.16; M36).

Furthermore, in the second quarter of 2024 consultations targeted to the citizenship will be organised, specially focused on assessing the perception and the awareness on upcycled products (nutraceuticals, plastics), their standardisation, their acceptance, etc. The surveys and questionnaires will be prepared based on validated tools during the last quarter of 2023 and first quarter of 2024

Surveys at the community-based scheme: These activities are embedded in the Task 7.1.2 and aim to further engage the public in the implementation of circular economy and the A2C model while collecting their feedback on the activities. To optimize the participation, citizens are rewarded, for which specific merchandising materials are collected. For instance,

Agro2Circular

¿Quieres llevarte a casa una cesta de alimentos locales y de temporada?

¡GRATIS PARA TI!

¡Participa en nuestro sorteo y gana la tuya!

Rellena esta encuesta y llévala al Puesto 1, Avda. de Juan Carlos I

GANA 20KG DE FRUTA Y VERDURA DE TEMPORADA

NOMBRE:
Nº DE TELÉFONO:

Acepto participar en el sorteo y proporcionar mis datos con fines de comunicación al ganador del sorteo.

1 SEÑALA LA DEFINICIÓN MÁS ADECUADA DE ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR:

La economía circular es un modelo de producción y consumo que implica compartir, alquilar, reutilizar, reparar, renovar y reciclar materiales y productos existentes todas las veces que sea posible para crear valor añadido.

Se trata de un modelo basado en producir, consumir y reciclar.

2 ¿RECICLAS DE FORMA HABITUAL?

Sí Casi Siempre A veces No

3 ¿RECICLA EN ALGUNO DE ESTOS CENTROS?

En casa En el trabajo Otros

4 SABÍAS QUE CON LOS RESIDUOS DE FRUTA Y VERDURA DE ESTE MERCADILLO SE PUEDE HACER:

Productos nutricionales Cosméticos Zumo y mermeladas Todo lo anterior

5 SABÍAS QUE CON LA ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR:

Cuida y respeta el planeta Es motor de empleo e Innovación Pueden generar fuentes renovables todas las anteriores

Logo of the European Union and the text: Este proyecto ha recibido financiación de la Comisión Europea a través del programa de Investigación e Innovación Horizonte 2020. El apoyo en el futuro está sujeto a la aprobación final de la Comisión.

Logo of PrimaFrio Fundación

Figure 20. Brochure with survey at the Alhama City market

PRIMA conducted a short survey included in a brochure (Figure 20) in April 2023, with questions exploring awareness and recycling behaviours of the citizens at the Alhama City market; the public taking part in the survey was involved in a draw, in which the prize consisted of a basket with 20 kg of fresh fruits and vegetables from the market itself. The results of the survey, answered by 94 people, will be used to evaluate the engagement in the community-based scheme and to design new actions. Further detail and lessons learnt will be displayed in the report on Community based innovation schemes (D7.4; M35).

Other consultations. The co-creation of the multidimensional model (Task 7.5) involves different tools, some of them at the consult level (surveys and interviews). These are based on a collection of statements designed by UVEG and KVC that provide feedback on different scenarios related with the dimensions of the A2C model (environmental, technological, socioeconomic, financial, regulatory, governance, training and awareness raising, and

standardisation). A total of 24 stakeholders participated in the survey and some of the participants showed availability for a deeper interview, which allowed longer responses and therefore a more detailed analysis. The results of the survey were subsequently discussed in workshops (one of them performed in July 2023, another planned for the last quarter of 2023), constituting a further level of participation (see 8.2.4).

Next steps

A further consultation is planned for T8.6 (focusing on the training dimension), using a questionnaire designed by UVEG. The main stakeholders targeted will be those related to academia and education, but also companies and professionals, as well as public administrations related to the A2C, in such a manner that the results provide insights on the materials and contents to be developed for the final version of the Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (D8.7; M35).

8.2.3 Involve [new]

The Involve level aims at *working with the public to make sure that their concerns and aspirations are considered and understood.*

Table 4 Involve activities calendar

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024
Community based.					Start			Summer break (June/ July)				Summer break (June/ July)
Circular game award						Training	Award			Training	Award	
Documentary							Shooting	Shooting/edition	Launch/publication			
Waste collections												

Community based scheme. Under task 7.1.2, a participative and community-based innovation (T7.1.2) has been organised by PRIMA, with the collaboration of KVC, CETEC, CTNC, AGROFOOD, MCT and EVERSIA, to foster the acceptance, awareness and knowledge of climate-neutral practices, alternatives, and behaviours but also aimed at strengthening communities, paying special attention to the challenges that disadvantaged and deprived communities may face. After preparatory meetings with the Alhama de Murcia City Council (particularly, the Local Development Department), and associations of market vendors, the activity started in November 2022. The scheme consisted of the installation of a booth at the City Market, that acted as A2C Face2face infrastructure (see section 7.4.2), and 6 containers in which the market vendors deposited the 6 types of fruit and vegetable waste considered in the project, to be sent to CTNC for further processing and incorporation to the A2C value chains (Figure 21). The community-based scheme has also served to distribute surveys, organize awards, and present products similar to those that will be the final results of the project, until June 2023, in which the activity was interrupted for summer break.

Next steps

PRIMA and KVC are organising new activities framed in the community-based scheme (consults, small seminars, awards, etc) to be restarted in October 2023 until the end of the project.

Moreover, the scheme will be expanded to other dates and special events, installing the booth and performing activities such as prizes, surveys, showcases-

The results and the lessons learnt from the community-based scheme will be published as Deliverable D7.4 (Report on Community based innovation schemes) on M35 of the project.

Figure 21 Pictures of the Community-Based scheme

Circular game award. Circular Game was an initiative to teach young people (Primary and secondary education) about circular economy in a fun and engaging way. With this aim, more than 300 students from different centres in Alhama and Murcia joined in groups to create videogames related to the circular economy using Arkade Makecode; to improve the circular and programming skills they needed, a series of seminars were organised from February to May 2023 (Figure 22). At the end of the activity the videogames designed were presented to take part in a **big contest** on circular economy videogames. After the evaluation of the videogames by a multidisciplinary jury, considering criteria related to the presence of circularity concepts, design and usability, the winners were awarded in a ceremony celebrated at PRIMA facilities in May 2023 (Figure 23).

Next steps

Given the success of the videogame course, partners involved will organize a new edition with the company TALENTOSTEM during the last year of the project. The dates are expected to be the same than last year.

Figure 22 Seminar for the development of the Circular Game

Figure 23 Circular Game awards at PRIMA facilities

Video documentary. Since January 2023, the local outreach desk has been collaborating in the elaboration of a collaborative video documentary. As a first step, a script was drafted to plan the contents, consisting of an introduction, the description of the different value chains addressed by the project, and finally different interviews with stakeholders in which the multidimensional aspect of the circular economy and the challenges and impacts for implementation are reflected through their impressions. Led by PRIMAFRIO, the documentary started the shooting stage in March, and the final result included all the parts will be presented in October 2023. In the meantime, 10 information pills corresponding to the interviews section have been uploaded to the project Youtube channel (Figure 24),

Next steps

4 additional pills will be published in September/October 2023, summing up 14 video pills. The video is expected to be published on October 2023 and disseminated in different events and channels

Figure 24 Video pills of interviews

Waste collections. In addition to the waste collection carried out in Task 7.1.2, further activities are being planned for the last year of the project, in collaboration with local and regional associations. The aim of these activities is to raise awareness on waste production and the need of a circular economy, fostering sustainable behaviours among citizens and promoting the participation of end-users, especially vulnerable groups, in the project.

Next steps

These activities, organized in coordination with community leaders and CSOs, will be framed in the community-based schemes and activities with educational centres.

8.2.4 Collaborate [new]

The Collaborate level has the objective of partnering with the public in each aspect of the decision-making process, which requires repeated and iterative interactions and creative feedback techniques.

Table 5. Collaborate activities calendar

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
	Q4 2021	Q1 2022	Q2 2022	Q3 2022	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023	Q4 2023	Q1 2024	Q2 2024	Q3 2024
Stakeholder panel												
Workshops/ Focus groups				Engagement strategy			HOOP	T7.5 Model	T7.5 Model (policy rec)	T7.5/T8.6 (training)	T7.7 validation, clustering	

Set up of a stakeholder panel. After the mapping of stakeholders (first step of the Engagement Strategy drafting), several rounds of contact were performed to set up the stakeholder panel. The members were selected to represent the sectors related to the A2C (agrifood sectors, plastic recycling, packaging, agriculture, biotechnology, bioeconomy & circular economy, environment, policy makers, SSH & gender), and the different parts of the quadruple helix (see section 5). To ensure the manageability, 2 different panels were created, each of them composed by 8 experts (2 from public administration, 2 from the industry, 2 from civil society and 2 from research and education). The aim of the regional panel (Table 5) is to collaborate with the Consortium during the project developments, providing feedback and attending to cocreation workshops under task 7.5 while avoiding language barriers. The EU stakeholder panel (Table 6) has a parallel composition and is involved in the validation of the multidimensional model for the adoption and scale up, and the elaboration of policy reviews (under task 7.7). The members of the Stakeholders Panels have signed a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA), together with the A2C coordinator, to certify their participation, ensure the fulfilment of ethical aspects and data protection requirements. The activities of the Stakeholder Panel have no related costs and are considered in-kind contributions. The list may slightly change due to right of withdraw included in the NDA or the reinforcement with additional actors.

Table 6 Regional stakeholder panel

Sector/Type of entity	Entity & Level	Description/Rationale
Public Administration	Integrated Centre for Training and Agricultural Experiences Molina de Segura (dependent of	Organization of complementary and specialized training courses and actions, of regional, national and international scope, with the aim of updating and perfecting the technical skills of

	Regional Ministry of Agriculture)	professionals in the sector. Participation in research through demonstrations at their facilities.
Public Administration	Alhama City Council (Municipal level)	Department of Local Development and Commerce
Industry	AEMA (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia)	Environmental Businesses Association Region of Murcia. Including waste management, environmental consultancy, environmental quality, etc.
Research/Academia	Water eco-efficiency chair (Regional level)	University of Murcia
Research/Academia	Department of Tribology and materials	Polytechnical University Cartagena
Research/Academia	CETENMA (Regional level)	Environment research centre (private non for profit)
Civil Society	Ambiente Europeo (Regional level)	Specialized in CE and pollutions issues, collaboration with industries
Civil Society	Ecologistas en Acción Región Murciana	Environmentalist association with experience on impacts of with agrifood sector

Table 6. EU Stakeholder Panel

Sector/Type of entity	Entity & Level	Description/Rationale
Consumer Association	Unione Nazionale Consumatori Umbria (Italy)	Unione Nazionale Consumatori (UNC) is the first consumer association in Italy.
Industry	Digiotech (Estonia)	ICT innovations and services through its participation in EU Horizon 2020 projects and strong in-house R&D. The company is experienced with Standard Development on IoT, Web of Things, and Digital Transformation
Industry	FILSE SPA (Italy)	Consultancy in Liguria (Italy) supports region (public administrations) in development of policies and interventions
Industry	Agrotransilvania Cluster (Romania)	Technology transfer centre of RDI in agro-industrial field at national level.
Research/Academia	Veltha (Italy)	Research centre; development of Policies for Sustainable Development and Social Innovation
Research/Academia	Aalborg University (Denmark)	Packaging technology, packaging machinery and press-forming, heat sealing and converting of fibre-based materials.
Public Administration	Municipality of Nea Smyrni (Greece)-	Deputy Mayor. Implementation of circular projects related to food waste.

Workshops. Up to date, 3 workshops have been conducted:

- The first workshop served to validate the ecosystem analysis of the engagement strategy and draft the actions to be performed in the following months. The results of this workshop are detailed in section 8.1
- The second workshop was organised jointly with the HOOP project, as one of the Biowaste Clubs that take part in the city of Murcia, hosted by the Circular Education Lab. The workshop aimed at addressing the challenges that the regional industry faces to implement the circular bioeconomy and identify opportunities for collaboration. Regional partners of the project (CETEC, KVC, CTNC, SOLPLAST, GWC, MCT, PROEX, INFO) attended the workshop (Figure 25, together with stakeholders (UPCT, CETENMA and Science for Change-SfC). The workshop also highlighted the importance of collaboration and synergy between different actors and the need for development and improvement of cutting-edge technologies, to fill the existing gaps in circular value chains.

Figure 25. Joint workshop with the HOOP project: Biowaste Club

- The third workshop was held on July 7, 2023 at the headquarters of the INFO in Murcia. In this workshop, organised jointly by KVC and UVEG (Figure 26). The organizations and companies represented in the workshop were members of the Driving Group (CETEC, CJM, PRIMA, INFO, MCT, Regenera, GWC, EVERSIA, AGROFOOD) and the regional Stakeholder Panel (CETENMA, AEMA, UPCT, CIFEA, Alhama Municipality and Ecologistas en Acción). During the workshop, the results of the survey carried out electronically between June 15 and June 26, 2023 were presented, with the objective of gathering in first-hand the feedback of the participants about the results and validate with them the generalization of the multidimensional model that is being developed under T7.5, through the decontextualization of the statement of the items. The dimensions treated were: Environmental, Socioeconomic, Technological, Governance, Regulatory, Financial, Standardization and Training. For each dimension there were a series of items (challenges) that were assessed on the basis of the relevance for the adoption of the Circular Economy.

Figure 26. Workshop at INFO

Next steps

Within T7.5, other co-creation interactions and workshops are planned to create and validate the A2C model and self-assessment tool, covering different dimensions.

For instance, in T7.5.5, public procurers and relevant stakeholders involved in the A2C will be coordinated to further deepen the engagement between these key stakeholders in the region of Murcia

In T7.7, the workshops will be aimed at the validation of the model and the tool in different regions, for which the EU stakeholders' level will be engaged in the following months. This way, the continuation of the workshop carried out in July will continue with a second workshop in November 2023, to be held online, with the regional stakeholder panel and particularly focused on policy recommendations. Moreover, focus groups will be organised from the second trimester of 2024 onwards, on the topic of training and capacity building for public engagement in circular economy projects and other environmental fields.

8.2.5 Empower [updated]

The Empower level has the objective of *placing final decision-making in the hands of the public, requiring the development of stable participation, monitoring and evaluation structures that have competencies and decision-making capacity.*

There are no activities in A2C at the empower level. On the other hand, it is considered that the empower level is reached through the involvement in the decision making and policies processes. This entails 3 conditions:

- An enhanced awareness about the circular economy, the territory and the sectors involved.
- The deployment of capacity building mechanisms at the individual and collective level.
- The generation of a favourable environment allowing the development of an active and binding participation

8.3 Monitoring and Evaluation

It is recommendable to establish monitoring and evaluation processes throughout the public participation process, incorporating criteria and indicators defined in a qualitative and participative manner. Continuous monitoring and evaluation allow us to rectify processes and results when required and to adapt to the current context, taking advantage of arising opportunities. This activity is foreseen within T7.3 led by KVelocity with the collaboration of

UVEG for social and economic evaluation at the project scope and will take into consideration of the cultural criteria indicating the involvement of all sectors of the population at the local level (for the community-based scheme), the regional level (for the systemic model) and if there are population groups that are being excluded.

Likewise, the participatory process in A2C should be subject of a specific evaluation, parallel to the social impact evaluation. Indicators established for the evaluation must consider different scopes (short term to long term, local to regional and EU) and cover aspects such as the degree of involvement and the degree of participation perceived in the A2C space.

9 Dissemination and Communication

‘Citizen engagement requires good communication – but good communication alone is not citizen engagement’.

Alec Walker-Love, Europe-based communications specialist with a background in urban mobility

During the elapsed time since the beginning of the project (October 2021) and the publication of this document (October 2022), project partners have made efforts to spread the project through the main website. In addition, a local website in Spanish was published, reinforcing the dissemination and communication of the events and activities at the local and regional levels in Alhama de Murcia and the Region of Murcia, where the project has been introduced. Furthermore, dissemination and communication materials in Spanish with a stronger focus on the activities carried out in the community-based scheme are being elaborated. These are the brochures and posters that will complement the video subtitled in Spanish.

The most important content of the actions will be sent to local and regional media to publish them. To reach and engage citizens in the activities, a clear and simple communication strategy has been put in place. Catchy messages are tailor made to the different stakeholders in the quadruple helix (public administrations, citizens and vendors from the market, educational centres, industry).

Once the general aim of the project has been explained to the citizens, the actions will be segmented according to the degree of citizen involvement and the type of public. To this end, several ways are currently being evaluated, from dedicated and programmed marketing campaigns to informative and awareness raising actions aimed at the citizens of Alhama de Murcia and the autonomous region.

9.1 Approach

Communication covers a wide range of actions targeted to several stakeholders or target audiences and should also communicate evidence-based information about areas and contents related to the project. In the case of A2C, these contents may among others relate to the impacts of plastics in the environment, the routes followed by the F&V waste from the collection in markets or by producers to the obtention of new products, the creation of new value chains, the need of governance, and regulatory and financing tools to put in place circular economy models. These contents may be produced by the consortium but also by third parties. A responsible innovation communication must select, curate and disseminate contents based on validated information, and make them easily understandable for all.

The most important objective (primary objective) is to engage citizens in the activities planned for the co-creation of a multidimensional circular economy model at the regional level, which can be replicated in other geographical contexts. Secondly, it is intended to engage and involve several stakeholders (research and academia, public administration, companies and investors, among others, to be detailed in Annex).

The communication activity in A2C in Murcia will allow the collection and distribution of data to optimise the engagement rate of all target groups, taking into consideration those that play a role as multipliers (civil society entities, NGOs, foundations, cultural centres, etc.).

9.2 Local Outreach Desk

The Local Outreach Desk was established in WP8, led by PRIMAFRIO and includes personnel from KVC, AGRO, CARM, and INFO. As shown in table 8, the Local Outreach Desk is also closely related to the A2C Outreach Manager (ICONS) and has a strong relationship with other institutional bodies, some of whom have already signed letters of support to state their interest in the project.

Team Members	Esther Ballester (PRIMAFRIO) Irene Garre (PRIMAFRIO) Aran Blanco (KVC) Ana Belén Morales (AGROFOOD) Beatriz Vallina (KVC)
Relation with Institutional Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instituto de Fomento (INFO) ● Instituto tecnológico del Calzado y el Plástico (CETEC) ● Instituto Tecnológico de la Conserva (CTNC) ● Ayuntamiento de Murcia ● Ayuntamiento de Alhama de Murcia ● Universidad de Murcia (UMU) ● Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT)
Relation with other WPs and partners	ICONS (A2C Outreach Manager) – WP8 WP8 partners

As indicated in the A2C outreach strategy (8.1), the Local Outreach Desk led by PRIMAFRIO will be responsible for defining the local D&C strategy, including the appropriate channels, messages and communication formats to foster engagement.

9.3 Communication Strategy

Engagement in communication refers to the community and aims at reaching a long-term alliance with a certain audience that allows sustaining knowledge, fostering the adoption of more culture-centric expressions of problems, solution-finding processes and facilitating structural transformations [9],[10]. Engagement is not restricted to interaction, the participation in demonstrators or involvement in a predefined period, while these could be considered as dimensions or outputs: **engagement means a medium and long-term sustainable relationship with feasible changes at the behavioural level.** In addition, the engagement of audiences contributes to the sustainability of the A2C project in the medium and long-term (Hanson et al., 2009).

This strategy considers that a multi-channel approach merging traditional and innovative media could contribute to accomplishing the objective as expressed in the project proposal. This way, the partners based in the Region of Murcia where the A2C model will be co-created and implemented will attend and organise specific events while using their networks and their influence through interpersonal and direct communication, social media and also traditional press and mass media (at the local level, in line with the project scope). The

actions planned are further detailed in section 8.2. The communication strategy should also consider opposition research, specific audience targeting, and continuous adjustment of the messages provided, when required, linked to the follow-up of the actions and responses obtained (including audiences' reactions and unintended results).

A double approach (upstream and downstream) will be used in A2C dissemination and communication for engagement.

- **Upstream:** refers to reaching a group that has interpersonal influence and can create change due to its relationship with the service-users instead of directly targeting the service-users (for example, citizens, companies or professionals in the agricultural sector). In addition, these groups could be more likely to influence and have the ability to modify contextual factors. For instance, policy-makers, public administration officers, community leaders or investors are groups to be considered in upstream actions.

- **Downstream:** to recruit service users for the A2C project will involve a significant effort in social marketing and public communication. Efforts should be made to design and implement the campaigns responding to the specific needs and preferences of citizens and main sub-targets.

It must be taken into consideration that upstream initiatives might be necessary for downstream efforts to be effective.

9.3.1 Goal and Objectives

The goal of the dissemination and communication within the engagement strategy is to recruit and engage the citizens in the municipality of Alhama de Murcia (for the community-based scheme) and by extension, the Region of Murcia, as it is explained in section 5.

The objectives are:

- To increase the impact of the engagement strategy.
- To engage citizens in other activities of the project.
- To communicate the project outcomes.
- To ensure the long-term sustainability of the project demonstrating the success and acceptance of the A2C multidimensional model among the involved stakeholders.

9.3.2 Target Audience

Citizen engagement and communication campaigns, even when they appear to address the general public, are directed toward specific segments of the population as seen in Figure 14.

Figure 28. Target groups aligned with the Quadruple Helix of Innovation

Some campaigns often include more than one target audience and can include both upstream and downstream groups. These groups are further explained in 6.2, while section 9.4 establishes the segmentation to sustain the engagement.

9.3.3 Media

A2C communication campaigns at the local level will require the media mentioned in D8.1 (platforms, online social media, mass media, interpersonal channels, small group meetings, and one-to-one discussions). The media of choice will depend on the key message and specific audiences for each communication campaign, as shown in Table 9.

9.3.4 Resources and Calendar

The table summarises the resources for supporting the citizen engagement strategy through the communication strategy. These resources will be considered for designing the communication campaigns plan, grouped depending on the actions and the specific degrees of participation, target audiences, tools and channels.

Each communication campaign should specify a calendar, considering the following phases:

- **Launch phase:** where the campaign is being initiated, involving the greatest media presence.
- **Body of the campaign:** where media are often used incrementally to remind the audiences of the message of the campaign.
- **Final media push:** before the campaign ends.

9.4 Main Communication Campaigns [updated]

Communication Campaigns (CC) comprise the overall organisation of the communication strategy and are in line with the action plan (section 8.2). Five types of communication campaigns are planned, according to Table 7. Campaigns are ordered from a lower to a higher degree of use of resources and media effort.

The campaigns will be carried out in Spanish to be understood by the local Spanish speaking public.

Table 7. Communication campaigns for public engagement

ID	Aim	Target group	Key message	Approach	Channels	Resources
INFORM						
CC1.1	To inform stakeholders about the A2C project.	Society as a whole	<i>A2C will develop and test its circular approach in a real case demo site</i>	Downstream	Local press/TV/radio Social media Local website	Current media presence. Flyer ¹¹ Posters
CC1.2	To disseminate the concept and results		<i>That's how A2C works. We'll keep you up to date!</i>	Downstream	Website Social media Local press, TV or radio Knowledge transfer and training	Personal networks and relations with Media Events (i.e., Science Week)
CONSULT						
CC2.1	To obtain valuable information and feedback	Citizens, service users (food, cosmetic, plastic industry)	<i>Without you, A2C does not make sense. Let us know your opinion!</i>	Downstream	Website A2C virtual platform Social media Local press, TV or radio	A2C virtual platform Partner's platforms (links) Social media Local press, TV or radio
CC2.2		Research and education	<i>A2C provides valuable information on how feedback can be obtained and analyzed to implement multidimensional and participatory circular economy models.</i>	Upstream	Personal relations with university chairs, departments Events and conferences	Current media presence. New tools for feedback gathering (surveys, questionnaires)
INVOLVE						

¹¹ In addition to the flyer designed in WP8 for the project, specific flyers for the local level are to be designed by PRIMAFRIO and KVC

ID	Aim	Target group	Key message	Approach	Channels	Resources
CC3.1	To recruit citizens for co-creating a circular model for the agrifood sector expecting a high degree of involvement and collaboration.	Citizens, service users (farmers), NGOs	<i>Your waste is your treasure. Out of food waste, new food can arise. Your participation is key to achieve the circularity of the F&V sector in the region. Participate in our event [substitute by the name of the event in each case]</i>	Downstream	Events Community based scheme (T7,1.2) Video documentary Local press/TV/radio Social media A2C Virtual platform Local website	Current media presence. Flyers and posters ¹³ Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
CC3.2		Industry (Agrofood, cosmetic, plastics) Investors	<i>Invest in a sustainable economic model for the future of agriculture. Participate in our events [substitute by the name of the event in each case]</i>		A2C Virtual platform Local website Events Newsletter	
CC3.3		Public administrations Policy makers	<i>A sustainable and circular model must encompass regulatory, economic and governance aspects to become a success. Participate in our events [substitute by the name of the event in each case]</i>	Upstream	A2C Virtual platform Local website Events	
CC3.4		Research and education	<i>Community-engaged projects could contribute to filling the gap in implementation research. Join our online forum!</i>		Training and knowledge transfer	
COLLABORATE CC4	To involve citizens in the decision-	Citizens Private/Industry Administration	<i>We need your participation in the decision-making.</i>	Downstream	Personal networks Events	Current media presence Flyers

ID	Aim	Target group	Key message	Approach	Channels	Resources
	making process through the collaboration and consultation with the public in all relevant areas	Research & Education (Stakeholder panel) Other projects in the call	<i>We want to hear your voice: Join the decision-making process now.</i>		Local press/TV/radio Social media A2C Virtual platform Local website	Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media
EMPOWER CC5	To raise loyalty and engagement during the pilot implementation	Service-users (i.e., citizens, vendors, farmers people participating and already involved)	<i>In A2C we are implementing a participatory circular economy model. We want to hear your voice.</i>	Downstream	Local press/TV/radio Social media A2C Virtual platform Local website	Current media presence Webinars Presentations Personal networks and relations with media

10 CONCLUSIONS

The objectives of public engagement in A2C are:

- ✓ To involve all the stakeholders (a quadruple helix of participation) in co-creation processes;
- ✓ To foster a systemic change towards new behavioural models, financing methods, policies, etc;
- ✓ To improve the awareness and acceptance of climate-neutral circular economy practices;
- ✓ To increase the deployment of circular solutions and their adoption at the regional level, to be later replicated in other contexts.

The Deliverable 7.3 Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results of the Agro2Circular project will still require continuous revision and updating, particularly the dissemination and communication section. to ensure the foreseen objectives and goals allowing the long-term sustainability of the model proposed in A2C. The impact of the dissemination has been analysed in WP8 deliverables, including the activities at the inform level.

At the regional and local level, there is a wide variety of stakeholders and participation infrastructures, having as a purpose citizen engagement at all levels (Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate, Empower).

At the consult level, the participation has been satisfactory (in terms of the number of surveys answered by stakeholders and citizens in activities 7.1.2, 7,4 and 7,5) and further consultations will be planned. Also, at the involvement level, the community-based scheme has revealed as a good tool to attract the interest of citizens and will continue until the end of the project, combining with other activities and paying more attention to the dissemination aspect, while the collection of F&W waste was considered not cost effective for the purposes of the project. This will be further analysed in D7.4. Likewise, the seminars and workshops in educational schools will continue to transfer the knowledge acquired in coordination with T8.6. For the collaborate level, the co-creation workshops to deliver and to validate the A2C model will continue during the last year of the project within the tasks 7.5 and 7.7.

The involvement of relevant actors in the stakeholder panels set up has also provided relevant insights. Although the building of these panels was challenging especially for the public administration sector, the collaboration of the partners providing their networks has played a key role.

11 ANNEXES

11.1 Stakeholder list

11.1.1 Public Administration/services

11.1.1.1 Regional

Table 8. Public administration sector stakeholders at the regional level

Regional Government (Partner):
Regional Ministry of Business, Employment, Universities and Spokeswoman
Regional Ministry of Education
Regional Ministry of Transparency, Citizen Participation and Public Administration
Public Services
Instituto de Fomento (INFO) (partner)
Scientific Park in Murcia (depending on INFO, hosts technological businesses)
Official Commerce Chambers (Murcia, Cartagena, Lorca)
Fundación Séneca (Science and Technology Agency)

11.1.1.2 Local

Table 9. Public administration sector stakeholders at the local level

Local Government: City Hall of Alhama de Murcia Departments
Infrastructures, Public Services, Energy Efficiency, Administrative Environmental Management, Public Contracts Department
Associations, Transparency, Citizen Engagement, New technologies, Sports, Internal affairs, Dependencies and Transport Department
Equality, Social Welfare, Older people, and Consumption Department
Citizen service, Urban Quality, Parks and Gardens Department
Development, Employment, Commerce, Hospitalities Department
Youth, New Technologies, Environment, Animal Welfare Department

11.1.2 Private sector

Table 10. Private sector stakeholders at the regional level

Private Organisations and Industry (End-Users)			
Food			
Agrícola Santa Eulalia	Agridemur	AgroCazalla	Agrodolores El Mirador
Agromark	AgroMediterránea	Hortiberia	Hortofruticola 3 Puentes
Mercagrisa	Peregrin	Cota 120	Soltir
SUBASUR	Surinver	Deilor	Difrusa
Almerca	Cricket	El Montes	Puerto Export
Kernel	KPE	Sabas	Urcisol
Adesur	AgroTomy	Peregrin	Camposeven
Sacoje	Verdimed	Florette	Paloma
Fruca	G's	Tana	Cítricos de Murcia
AMC	J Garcia Carrión	Cynara	Marín Gimenez
Hida Alimentación	Manuel García	Alkácil	
	Campoy		
Cosmetics			

Aromsa			
Iberchem			
Natuaromatic			
Nutraceuticals			
Nutrafur			
HTBA			
Plastic Producers and recyclers			
Palec Ecologico	Galian Plastics	Onlyplast	Plasbel
Reciplast	Plastirama	Plastics Marin	Ros
Retailers, Supermarkets, Services			
Food chains (Aldi, Mercadona, Lidl, Spar, Superdumbo)			
SMEs, entrepreneurs (small supermarkets, market vendors, F&V local shops)			
Tourism and hospitality services: i.e., Foodtopia (restaurant/catering service engaged in reduction of food losses)			
Agrifood Clusters and Associations			
Agritech Murcia https://www.agritechmurcia.com/			
Industrial and Business Associations			
Asemuplast (Region of Murcia)			
AMIQ (Association of Chemical Industries in the Region of Murcia)			
AEMA RM (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia)			
AGRUPAL (Association of Canning Industries)			
FECOAM (Association of Agricultural Cooperatives)			
Financing Intermediaries			
Caja Rural Central			
Globalcaja			
Caja Rural Regional			
Private Non-Profit Organisations			
CETENMA - Technological Centre for Energy and Environment			
CEEIM- Business and Technological Centre in Murcia			
CEEIC- Business and Technological Centre in Cartagena			

11.1.3 Citizens and Civil society organisations

Table 11. Civil society organisations related to A2C at regional level

Environmental Associations
Ambiente Europeo
Región de Murcia Limpia
Murcia Residuo Cero
Teachers for future, Fridays for future, parents for future
Ecologistas en Acción
ANSE- Asociación de Naturalistas del Sureste
Education Associations
Confederación Regional De Asociaciones De Madres Y Padres De Alumnos De Murcia "CONFAMUR"
Consumer Organisations (and others)
Federación murciana de asociaciones de amas de casa, consumidores y usuarios THADER
Asociación de Consumidores y Usuarios en Red, CONSUMUR

REAS MURCIA – Alternative and Solidary Economy Network
Professional Associations and Trade Unions
Agronomic Engineers Official College
Agricultural Engineers and Agricultural Technicians Official College
Environmentalists Official College (COAMBRM)
Chemists Official College (COLQUIMUR)
Biologists Official College
Veterinarians Official College
Asociación de Biotecnólogos de la Región de Murcia (BIOTECMUR)
ASAJA (Agricultural Association of Young Farmers)
COAG-IR (Coordination Entity of Farmers and Stockbreeders)
UPA (Union of small farmers)
Associations of market vendors

Table 12. Civil society organisations related to A2C at local level

Environmental Associations
Asociación ECOESPUÑA
Asociación Centro de Desarrollo humano y Educación ambiental, Ashram Jardín de Alhama
Asociación "La Almajara" de Alhama de Murcia
Asociación "La Hojarasca, educación por naturaleza"
Asociación de amigos de la agricultura - Las Barracas –
Asociación promotora de huertos urbanos. APHU
Asociación Red Agroconatura 2020
Consumer Organisations
Asociación De Amas De Casa, Consumidores Y Usuarios De Alhama de Murcia
Educational Organisations
Federación de Asociaciones De Padres De Alumnos de Alhama de Murcia (FAPA Alhama de Murcia)

11.1.4 Research and education

Table 13. Education and research entities at the regional level

UM (University of Murcia)
University Institute of Water and Environment (INUAMA)
PROSUR Chair on Food Biotechnology
Chair on Water and sustainability - EMUASA
Chair on Water ecoefficiency HIDROGEA
Chair on Food security and sustainability
Chair on Perfume and Cosmetic industry Natuaromatic
Chair Primafrio (logistics)
Open Chair for innovation and participation
Chair on Social Corporate Responsibility
Chair on social economy
Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT)
Chair on sustainable agriculture in Campo de Cartagena COAG
Chair G's Spain
Chair Logistics 4.0 Primafrio

Chair Agritech Chair Takasago
Universidad Católica San Antonio (UCAM)
Chair on Food for Health Chair on Sustainable Development Chair on Circular Economy and SCR Chair on biomaterial engineering Chair on Food Innovation Chair on Innovation in transport and logistics Primafrío Chair on Responsible Agrofood Systems Chair on Insect industrial production and Circular Economy in Biowaste management Chair on innovation in Fruit and Vegetable processing industry
UM & UPCT
Chair on Environment Autoridad Portuaria de Cartagena Campus Mare Nostrum
Research Centres
CEBAS- CSIC- Soil Science and Applied Biology Centre IMIDA – Region of Murcia Institute for Research and Agricultural and Environmental Development
CIFEAs (Integrated Centres for Agricultural Training and Experimentation)
CIFEA Jumilla CIFEA Lorca CIFEA Molina de Segura CIFEA Torre Pacheco

Table 14. Education and research entities at the local level

Primary Schools	Secondary Schools and VET centres	Primary and Secondary Schools
CEIP Sierra Espuña	IES Miguel Hernández*	Colegio Azaraque s. coop.* (private)
CEIP Príncipe de España	IES Valle de Leyva*	
CEIP Antonio Machado		
CEIP Nuestra Señora del Rosario		
CEIP Ginés Díaz -San Cristóbal		
CEIP Ricardo Codorníu		
CEIP Reina Sofía		
CEIP La Costera		

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